

to develop a complete package (CP = line sowing, fertilizer, weed and pest control, and bunding) and an intermediate package (IP = CP minus bunding). The traditional method consisted of broadcast seeding, no fertilizer or insect control, one hand weeding, and no bunding. There were eight randomized, replicated treatments with the local rice cultivar. LAC23.

The results (see table) show that traditional management produced lowest yields in both years. In 1981 there was no significant difference in grain yield among CP, IP, IP minus pest control, and IP minus line sowing. In 1982, however, both CP and IP had significantly higher

grain yields than the latter two treatments.

Regardless of treatment, weed infestation increased from 1981 to 1982. Grass weeds dominated, and grass and broadleaf weed infestation increased while sedges decreased. There were more weeds in IP minus weeding followed by the traditional method and IP minus line sowing.

In the second rice crop, grain yield with the traditional method (0.5 t/ha) could be doubled by adopting a package consisting of line sowing, fertilizer application, and weeding in areas where the population of destructive insect pests has not reached the economic threshold level.

In the third rice crop, grain yield with the traditional method (0.3 t/ha) could be tripled by line sowing, fertilizer application, weeding, and insect control. About 20% yield reduction can be expected if insecticide is not applied. However, armyworm *Spodoptera exempta*, which may invade upland rice fields after bush fallow, must be controlled by insecticide.

To maintain soil productivity and grain yields in consecutive rice crops after bush fallow, it is necessary to include crop rotation with legumes and other arable crops in the above package of agronomic practices. □

Effect of various agronomic practices on grain yield and number of weeds in upland continuous rice cultivation at Suakoko, Liberia (high rainfall zone).

Agronomic practice	Grain yield (t/ha)		Yield reduction (%) compared to IP		Weeds (no./m ²) at harvest							
					Grass		Sedges		Broadleaf		Total	
	1981	1982	1981	1982	1981	1982	1981	1982	1981	1982	1981	1982
Complete package (CP)	1.3 a	1.0 a	—	0.9	100	152	2	0	56	75	158	227
Intermediate package (IP = CP - bunding)	1.2 a	1.1 a	—	—	116	166	2	0	44	60	162	226
IP - fertilizer	0.6 b	0.5 c	49	50	108	150	2	0	61	54	171	204
IP - weeding	0.6 b	0.6 c	48	47	220	315	10	1	101	104	331	419
IP - line sowing	1.3 a	0.9 b	—	14	126	210	6	0	72	74	204	284
IP - insect control	1.3 a	0.8 b	—	20	114	154	3	1	43	75	160	230
Traditional method (control)	0.5 c	0.3 d	56	68	206	293	9	3	59	78	274	374
Traditional method + bunding	0.6 bc	0.4 d	52	66	192	244	18	1	46	92	256	337
CV (%)	5.8	10.4										
LSD (0.05)	0.08	0.11										

Rice response to zinc at various salinity and alkalinity levels

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A pot experiment studied rice response to Zn application in Rohi sandy loam soil (Typic Ustifluent, pH 7.4, no calcium carbonate, 0.5 ppm DTPA extractable Zn) treated with NaCl and NaHCO₃ to give initial electrical conductivities (EC) of 5, 10, and 20 mmho/cm at 25°C and exchangeable sodium percentages (ESP) of 10, 20, 40, and 60. Original and treated soils received 0 and 10 mg Zn/kg soil as ZnSO₄. A basal dose of 120 mg N, 13 mg P, and 30 mg K/kg soil from CO(NH₂)₂, KH₂PO₄, and KCl was ap-

plied to all pots. Five 30-day-old PR106 rice seedlings were transplanted in pots containing 10 kg soil and submerged in deionized water throughout the experiment.

Zn application increased dry matter yield (140% over the control) and the Zn content of rice straw (see table). As salt and alkali levels in soil increased, rice dry matter yield and Zn content significantly decreased. Adding Zn increased dry matter yield and Zn content of rice at all EC and ESP levels, but the effect was more pronounced in soils treated with salt than with alkali. Rice seedlings could not grow at EC of 20 mmho/cm and ESP of 60. Although adding Zn alleviated Zn deficiency, it did not offset the ill effects of high salinity and alkalinity levels on plant growth. □

Effect of Zn on dry matter yield and Zn content of rice straw.^a

Treatment ^b	Dry matter yield (g/10 kg soil)	Zn content (ppm)
EC 5	12.4	12.5
EC 5 + Zn	23.0	33.5
EC 10	0.5	12.1
EC 10 + Zn	4.2	29.2
ESP 10	10.6	12.2
ESP 10 + Zn	19.7	26.4
ESP 20	9.0	10.6
ESP 20 + Zn	15.8	20.6
ESP 40	5.5	9.7
ESP 40 + Zn	7.6	17.5
Original Soil	17.9	13.5
Original soil + Zn	42.9	41.4
CD at 5%	2.1	1.3

^a 85-day-old. ^b EC = electrical conductivity in mmho/cm at 25°C. ESP = exchangeable sodium percentage.